

EBFMC25-OP-54 · Examining the Effect of Virtual Family Formation on Assessing Family Adaptability and Unity

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ABSTRACT

Introduction: While virtual families can provide emotional support for some individuals, they may also lead to a weakening of relationships with real-life family members in certain cases. Studies have shown that virtual communities can be effective in developing the social skills of young individuals (Turkle, 2011), yet they may also cause disconnections in family communication (Subrahmanyam & Greenfield, 2008). Strong bonds formed by adolescents on digital platforms can lead them to question their real-life family roles and grow distant from their families. However, some research suggests that virtual families may play a healing role, particularly for individuals raised in dysfunctional family environments (Lenhart et al., 2015). This study aims to investigate the impact of digital family formations on family dynamics such as communication and cooperation, and to examine to what extent virtual relationships are included in family cohesion and unity alongside real-life relationships.

Materials and Methods: In this study, articles and theses related to families and social media between 2020 and 2025 were accessed through Google Scholar, the National Thesis Center of the Council of Higher Education, and ResearchGate. The studies were analyzed to determine which aspects of family dynamics they focused on and the perspectives from which they approached family interactions on social media.

Results: Although the literature search conducted in Turkish between 2020 and 2025 revealed studies on the impact of social media on intra-family interactions, no research was found specifically on virtual family formation. However, during the research, two relevant scales were accessed: the Family Adaptability and Cohesion Evaluation Scale, which assesses family dynamics in nine sub-dimensions, and the Virtual Family Scale presented at a congress. Following the necessary permissions, these scales will be applied to a selected sample using the relational correlational method. A personal information form will be included to determine which member of the family each participant represents. Data will be analyzed using the IBM SPSS statistical program to determine which sub-dimensions are related, the degree of the relationships, and whether significant differences exist.

Conclusion: This study aims to investigate the extent to which families in the age of social media associate their virtual dynamics with real-life family structures. It seeks to quantitatively assess and reveal whether families transfer their online interactions to their real-life bonds. If such an influence is identified, it will be suggested that the phenomenon of virtual family formation should be examined further by researchers in the field.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Virtual family, family cohesion, intra-family communication

INTRODUCTION

While virtual families can provide emotional support for some individuals, in certain cases, they may lead to the weakening of real family relationships. Studies have shown that virtual communities can effectively enhance the social skills of young individuals (Turkle, 2011) but may also cause disruptions in family communication (Subrahmanyam & Greenfield, 2008).

Especially during adolescence, the strong bonds formed on digital platforms may lead individuals to question their real-life family roles and distance themselves from their families. However, some research also indicates that virtual families can play a therapeutic role, especially for individuals raised in dysfunctional family environments (Lenhart et al., 2015).

This study aims to investigate the impact of digital family formation on family dynamics such as communication and cooperation and to examine to what extent families incorporate their virtual interactions into their perception of family unity. The objective is to identify the underlying dynamics of the social media phenomenon that affects the psychological structure of the family institution and to determine which dimensions are influenced and to what degree.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

For this study, academic articles and theses on family and social media between 2020 and 2025 were accessed via Google Scholar, the National Thesis Center of the Higher Education Council (YÖK), and ResearchGate. A total of 20 articles, 4 master's theses, and 2 conference papers were reviewed. This retrospective review aimed to systematically synthesize the existing knowledge accumulated during the specified time period.

The studies examined were analyzed in terms of which aspects of family dynamics they focused on and what perspectives they brought to the interactions within the family institution in the context of social media.

RESULTS

The literature review limited to Turkish-language studies published between 2020 and 2025 revealed that while there are studies on the effects of social media on intra-family interactions, no research was found specifically on the formation of virtual families. Through the non-open-access Toad database, a Family Adaptability and Cohesion Evaluation Scale -addressing nine different sub-dimensions of family dynamics-was accessed, as well as a Virtual Family Scale presented in a conference paper.

In 40% of the reviewed 20 articles (8 articles), communication sub-dimension and the dimensions of balanced cohesion and disengagement were the most prominent among the key aspects of the family institution. In all four master's theses, communication and unity emerged as the most significant family dimensions. Conference papers also consistently emphasized the communication dimension.

Virtual Family: This conceptual term describes a reality in which families spend most of their time on social media networks, interacting with each other—even with family members—through virtual channels. This masked communication causes individuals to disconnect from reality and prefer virtual interactions over real ones.

Family Adaptability and Cohesion: This term refers to the factors on which family harmony depends and how families assess their own unity. It is used to explore the necessary steps to strengthen family dynamics.

Balanced Cohesion: A situation in which family members are emotionally connected to one another.

- **Disengagement:** A state in which family members are emotionally distant from each other. This disconnection arises when members prefer or fail to maintain closeness with the family while preserving their autonomy.
- **Family Communication:** This refers to functional and positive communication skills within the family, such as empathic listening, unconditional acceptance, and honest expression of emotions among members.

CONCLUSION

Social media platforms now provide families with a new and significant space for interaction, altering traditional dynamics. In this context, the concept of “virtual family formation” represents the new perceptual and interactional reality emerging within the family framework due to social media. Family members may

perceive social media as a more effective tool for assessing unity, disconnection, and communication patterns compared to traditional methods—highlighting the growing role of social media in family functioning. Virtual family formation occupies an important place among the internal and external factors of the family institution and requires conceptual analysis. The tendency of families to prioritize virtual over real interactions shifts their perception of unity to a new dimension. This new dynamic should be integrated into fields such as family counseling, with its advantages and disadvantages carefully considered. Moreover, strategic steps should be taken to reduce the negative aspects of detachment from reality and to enhance the positive contributions of virtual family formation to family mental health.

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

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